

Strategies In Teaching Social Studies Among Junior High School Learners In Congressional District 1, Division Of Batangas Province

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Abstract

The study employs a descriptive research design to systematically present the current status of instructional strategies used by teachers and assess students' perceptions of their usefulness. Correlational analysis is conducted to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between these variables, offering insights into how the frequency and nature of strategy use influence students' perceived effectiveness.

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design, involving 139 Social Studies teachers selected through stratified random sampling. Data were gathered using a researcher-developed questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, weighted mean, ranking, and Pearson's r correlation coefficient. Results revealed that teachers highly utilized all four instructional strategies and perceived them as highly useful in promoting student engagement, critical thinking, and real-life application. A significant relationship was found between the extent of utilization and the degree of usefulness of instructional strategies. Major challenges identified included administrative workload, students' difficulty in relating lessons to real-life situations, and handling sensitive or controversial topics.

Based on the findings, the study proposed active learning and technology-integrated instructional activities to improve student engagement and learning outcomes. The study concludes that diversified and student-centered instructional strategies, supported by institutional assistance and professional development, are essential in enhancing the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction.

Keywords: *Social Studies instruction; instructional strategies; descriptive-correlational research; student engagement.*

Introduction

Social Studies is a vital component of the Junior High School curriculum as it fosters civic awareness, critical thinking, and a deeper understanding of historical and contemporary social issues. It plays a key role in developing well-informed and responsible citizens capable of contributing meaningfully to national development. In the Division of Batangas Province, particularly in Congressional District 1, teachers are tasked with delivering complex and sometimes abstract content in an engaging and relatable way to young learners. The effectiveness of this delivery depends largely on the strategies employed by educators to make the subject both accessible and relevant to students lived experiences.

This study will explore the various strategies for teaching Social Studies in secondary schools, focusing on the role of active learning, technology integration, and teacher development in enhancing student learning and engagement in Social Studies education in the Philippines context in Congressional District I, Schools Division of Batangas Province, school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of utilization of the instructional strategies in teaching as assessed by the teachers themselves with reference to:
 - 1.1 Traditional Teaching Strategies;
 - 1.2 inquiry-based learning;
 - 1.3 active learning strategies;
 - 1.4 technology integrated strategies?
2. How may the degree of usefulness of the instructional strategies be assessed in terms of:
 - 2.1 student engagement;
 - 2.2 critical thinking skills and problem-solving;
 - 2.3 connection to real-life situation?
3. Is there significant relationship between the assessments on the extent of utilization and on the degree of usefulness of the instructional strategies?
4. What challenges do teachers encounter in teaching Social Studies?
5. Based on the result, what instructional activities may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study will adopt a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive-correlational design. Descriptive research is utilized to systematically describe the current state of instructional strategies employed by teachers and to assess students' perceptions of their usefulness. Correlational analysis is then applied to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between these variables, providing insights into how the frequency and nature of strategy use relate to students' perceived effectiveness. Data will be collected through structured questionnaires administered to both teachers and students, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the instructional practices and their impacts. The study's design allows for the identification of patterns and associations, offering valuable information for educators and policymakers aiming to enhance Social Studies instruction in the region.

Participants

The subjects of this study consist of 139 Social Studies teachers from the 1st Congressional District of Batangas for the School Year 2024-2025. These teachers are responsible for delivering Social Studies education across various grade levels and educational institutions within the 1st congressional district. The research will utilize a stratified random sampling technique to ensure that teachers from different schools, educational levels, and backgrounds within the district are adequately represented. This method will allow for a comprehensive analysis of the teachers' experiences and practices while ensuring that each subgroup of Social Studies educators is proportionately included in the study.

Research Instrument

The data gathering instrument for this study consists of a survey questionnaire and interview designed to comprehensively assess various aspects of instructional strategies used in teaching Social Studies.

Questionnaire. The survey questionnaire will be developed based on the research questions and on some concepts found after reading related literature.

Interview Guide. An interview guide is a written framework containing questions, prompts, or themes that direct the flow of a research interview.

Data Collection Procedure

The data gathering procedure involved securing approval from school authorities and obtaining informed consent from participating Social Studies teachers to ensure ethical compliance and confidentiality. A survey questionnaire was administered, with follow-ups conducted to improve response rates and allow sufficient time for completion. Collected data were checked for completeness, coded, and organized according to key variables such as

instructional strategies, usefulness, and challenges, then analyzed using descriptive statistical methods. All responses were kept confidential, participation was voluntary, and the findings were summarized and shared with relevant stakeholders to support improvements in Social Studies instruction.

Data Analysis

Descriptive research method (questionnaire, ranking, weighted mean, inferential statistical test and Pearson's r correlation coefficient) were used to summarize responses.

Results

The results showed that Social Studies teachers utilized a combination of instructional strategies in teaching the subject.

Section 1: Extent of Utilization of Instructional Strategies

The findings indicate that Social Studies teachers continue to rely heavily on traditional teaching strategies.

Table 2
Extent of Utilization of Instructional Strategies in terms of
Traditional Teaching Strategies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I regularly use lectures to deliver Social Studies content in my classroom.	3.97	Highly Utilized	2
2. I employ question-and-answer sessions to check students' understanding during lessons.	3.98	Highly Utilized	1
3. I use textbook readings as a primary resource for teaching Social Studies topics.	3.91	Highly Utilized	3
4. I assign written exercises such as summaries and essays to reinforce learning.	3.89	Highly Utilized	5
5. I use storytelling to explain historical events and concepts in Social Studies.	3.94	Highly Utilized	4
Weighted Mean	3.94	Highly Utilized	

3.50–4.00 Highly Utilized 2.50–3.49 Moderately Utilized 1.50–2.49 Slightly Utilized 1.00–1.49 Least Utilized

The findings in Table 3 indicate that Social Studies teachers highly utilize inquiry-based learning strategies.

Table 3
Extent of Utilization of Instructional Strategies in terms of Inquiry-Based Learning

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I encourage students to ask questions and explore answers through guided inquiry activities.	3.95	Highly Utilized	1
2. I design lessons that require students to conduct research on Social Studies topics.	3.84	Highly Utilized	5
3. I use problem-solving tasks that stimulate student investigation and discovery.	3.91	Highly Utilized	3.5
4. I incorporate activities where students formulate hypotheses and test them.	3.91	Highly Utilized	3.5
5. I facilitate group discussions where learners analyze social issues critically.	3.93	Highly Utilized	2
Weighted Mean	3.91	Highly Utilized	

The findings in Table 4 indicate that Social Studies teachers highly utilize active learning strategies. These findings reinforce the view that active learning approaches are essential in contemporary Social Studies instruction, effectively shifting the focus from passive knowledge reception to meaningful, student-centered experiences that promote deeper comprehension and civic engagement.

Table 4
Extent of Utilization of Instructional Strategies in terms of Active Learning Strategies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I use role-playing or simulations to help students understand historical events or social concepts.	3.94	Highly Utilized	2
2. I integrate group projects that require collaboration among students.	3.87	Highly Utilized	4
3. I conduct debates on civic or social issues to encourage active participation.	3.89	Highly Utilized	3
4. I incorporate hands-on activities that involve students in constructing knowledge.	3.86	Highly Utilized	5
5. I use cooperative learning strategies to engage students interactively.	3.96	Highly Utilized	1
Weighted Mean	3.91	Highly Utilized	

The results in Table 5 demonstrate that teachers have successfully incorporated a range of technological tools to enhance engagement, interactivity, and relevance in Social Studies instruction, while also highlighting the need for ongoing professional development to ensure technology serves as a transformative, rather than merely supplementary, element of learning.

Table 5
Extent of Utilization of Instructional Strategies in terms of
Technology-Integrated Strategies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I use multimedia presentations (videos, slideshows) during Social Studies lessons.	3.95	Highly Utilized	2
2. I incorporate interactive digital tools such as virtual maps or timelines in my teaching.	3.93	Highly Utilized	3.5
3. I utilize online resources or educational apps to supplement Social Studies instruction.	3.93	Highly Utilized	3.5
4. I assign students to use the internet for research and information gathering.	3.89	Highly Utilized	5
5. I integrate technology like virtual reality or simulations to provide immersive learning experiences.	3.96	Highly Utilized	1
Weighted Mean	3.93	Highly Utilized	
3.50–4.00 Highly Utilized 2.50–3.49 Moderately Utilized 1.50–2.49 Slightly Utilized 1.00–1.49 Least Utilized			

Section 2: Degree of Usefulness of Instructional Strategies.

The degree of usefulness of instructional strategies refers to how effectively teaching methods support learning objectives, engage students, and enhance academic achievement. It helps identify which approaches—such as technology integration, collaborative learning, or differentiated instruction—best meet learners' diverse needs.

The data shows teachers' perceptions of how useful five instructional strategies are for promoting student engagement in Social Studies.

Table 6
Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies in terms of Student Engagement

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The use of group discussions in Social Studies lessons is useful in keeping students actively involved.	3.91	Highly Useful	3
2. Role-playing activities help increase students' participation during Social Studies classes.	3.88	Highly Useful	5
3. Interactive multimedia presentations are useful for maintaining students' attention throughout the lesson.	3.91	Highly Useful	3
4. Hands-on projects encourage students to stay engaged and interested in Social Studies topics.	3.95	Highly Useful	1
5. Debates on current social issues promote active student involvement in the classroom.	3.91	Highly Useful	3
Weighted Mean	3.91	Highly Useful	

3.50–4.00 Highly Useful 2.50–3.49 Need Useful 1.50–2.49 Slightly Useful 1.00–1.49 Least Useful

The findings in Table 7 support recent research highlighting the value of inquiry-based and experiential learning for developing critical thinking.

Table 7
Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies in terms of Critical Thinking Skills and Problem Solving

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Inquiry-based learning strategies are useful in developing students' critical thinking skills in Social Studies.	3.96	Highly Useful	1
2. Problem-solving activities based on historical scenarios enhance students' analytical abilities.	3.90	Highly Useful	4
3. Using case studies in Social Studies lessons helps students practice reasoning and decision-making.	3.90	Highly Useful	4
4. Assignments that require evaluating multiple perspectives improve students' critical thinking.	3.90	Highly Useful	4
5. Simulations and role-playing activities contribute to students' problem-solving skills.	3.92	Highly Useful	2
Weighted Mean	3.92	Highly Useful	

3.50–4.00 Highly Useful 2.50–3.49 Need Useful 1.50–2.49 Slightly Useful 1.00–1.49 Least Useful

The data in Table 8 show that linking Social Studies instruction to real-life contexts enhances learning, engagement, and civic awareness.

Table 8
Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies in terms of Connection to Real-Life Situation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Project-based learning helps students relate Social Studies concepts to their community and everyday life.	3.90	Highly Useful	4
2. Using current events as discussion topics makes Social Studies more relevant and useful to students.	3.92	Highly Useful	3
3. Field trips or virtual tours to historical sites effectively connect lessons to real-world contexts.	3.88	Highly Useful	5
4. Activities that involve analyzing social issues improve students' understanding of their role in society.	3.94	Highly Useful	2
5. Assignments that ask students to apply Social Studies concepts to personal experiences are useful in making learning meaningful.	3.98	Highly Useful	1
Weighted Mean	3.92	Highly Useful	

3.50–4.00 Highly Useful 2.50–3.49 Need Useful 1.50–2.49 Slightly Useful 1.00–1.49 Least Useful

Section 3: Relationship between the Assessments on the Extent of Utilization and the Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies.

Statistical analysis revealed a significant relationship between the extent of utilization and the degree of usefulness of instructional strategies. This indicates that instructional strategies that were more frequently used by teachers were also perceived as more useful in enhancing student engagement, critical thinking, and real-life application. The result suggests that consistent and effective use of varied instructional strategies contributes positively to the perceived effectiveness of Social Studies instruction.

Table 9

Significant Relationship between the Assessments on the Extent of Utilization and the Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies in terms of Student Engagement

Indicators	Correlations		P – value	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
STUDENT ENGAGEMENT	Traditional Teaching Strategies	.950	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Inquiry-Based Learning	.981	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Active Learning Strategies	.945	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Technology Integrated Strategies	.941	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

TABLE 10

Significant Relationship between the Assessments on the Extent of Utilization and the Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies in terms of Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving

CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS AND PROBLEM-SOLVING	Traditional Teaching Strategies	.949	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Inquiry-Based Learning	.963	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Active Learning Strategies	.939	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Technology Integrated Strategies	.941	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

TABLE 11

Significant Relationship between the Assessments on the Extent of Utilization and the Degree of Usefulness of the Instructional Strategies in terms of Connection to Real Life Situation

CONNEC -TION TO REAL- LIFE SITUA- TION	Traditional Teaching Strategies	.925	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Inquiry-Based Learning	.944	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Active Learning Strategies	.925	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Technology Integrated Strategies	.950	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Section 4: Challenges Teachers Encounter in Teaching Social Studies

Table 12
Challenges Teachers Encounter in Teaching Social Studies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I lack sufficient instructional time to cover the entire Social Studies curriculum.	2.61	Agree	10
2. I find it difficult to engage students who are not interested in Social Studies.	2.64	Agree	9
3. There are not enough updated and relevant teaching materials available for Social Studies.	2.79	Agree	7
4. Large class sizes hinder my ability to effectively implement interactive teaching strategies.	2.80	Agree	6
5. I am not given enough professional development opportunities related to teaching Social Studies.	2.81	Agree	5
6. I face challenges in using technology effectively in my Social Studies instruction.	2.76	Agree	8
7. Discussing sensitive or controversial topics in Social Studies makes me uncomfortable or unsure.	2.86	Agree	3
8. Students struggle to relate Social Studies lessons to real-life situations.	2.88	Agree	2
9. I often experience stress or burnout related to teaching Social Studies.	2.84	Agree	4
10. Administrative workload and non-teaching responsibilities interfere with my preparation for Social Studies classes.	2.91	Agree	1
Weighted Mean	2.79	Agree	

3.50–4.00 Strongly Agree 2.50–3.49 Agree 1.50–2.49 Disagree 1.00–1.49 Strongly Disagree

The data highlight the need for institutional support and professional development to address challenges in Social Studies instruction. Providing adequate preparation time, resources, training, and reduced administrative workload can empower teachers to deliver meaningful, engaging, and socially responsive lessons, enhancing both teacher confidence and student learning outcomes.

Section 5: Propose Activities for Active Learning and Technology Integration in Enhancing Student Learning and Engagement in Social Studies Education

The researcher proposed the develop Interactive Strategies such as Kahoot Quizzes, Think-Pair and Share, Small Group Discussion and Whole Class Discussion and Reflection. Also, it is also included the Cooperative and Experiential Learning such as Role Play. In addition, is the Technology Integrated Strategies wherein the students will allow to use technological strategies in learning such as PowerPoint- and Video-Supported Lesson Delivery, Multimedia, Infographics, and Visual Aid Integration and Online Games. Lastly, is the Real-Life and Contextual Learning different Performance based Projects.

Discussion

The results suggest that diversified and student-centered instructional strategies significantly enhance the teaching and learning of Social Studies. Consistent with existing literature, inquiry-based and active learning approaches promote deeper understanding, critical thinking, and meaningful engagement among junior high school learners. However, the continued reliance on traditional strategies reflects systemic constraints rather than pedagogical preference.

The significant relationship between utilization and usefulness underscores the importance of sustained support for teachers in implementing effective instructional strategies. Addressing challenges such as limited resources, inadequate training, and large class sizes is essential for maximizing the impact of innovative teaching approaches. Based on the findings, the study proposes instructional activities that integrate inquiry, collaboration, technology, and real-life applications to strengthen Social Studies instruction in the local context.

Overall, the study highlights the need for continuous professional development, improved access to instructional resources, and institutional support to enhance the quality of Social Studies education among Junior High School learners in the Division of Batangas Province.

Conclusion

The following are conclusions drawn from the results presented on the previous chapter.

1. The teachers highly utilized the instructional strategies in Social Studies, such as traditional, inquiry-based, active, and technology-integrated strategies.
2. Similarly, the teachers themselves assessed that the instructional strategies were highly useful.
3. It is indicated that there is a significant relationship in the usefulness of the utilization of the instructional strategies.

4. The top 3 challenges faced by teachers are 1. Administrative workload and non-teaching responsibilities interfere with my preparation for Social Studies classes; 2. Students struggle to relate Social Studies lessons to real-life situations, and discussing sensitive or controversial topics in Social Studies makes me uncomfortable or unsure.

5. It is concluded that a Proposed Activities for Active Learning, Technology Integration, and Teacher Development in Enhancing Student Learning and Engagement in Social Studies Education will be created.